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FORMATION OF INNOVATIVE ECONOMY ON THE BASIS OF MARKET PRINCIPLES

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ НА ОСНОВЕ РЫНОЧНЫХ ПРИНЦИПОВ

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Abstract. The significance of innovative economy for government is its influence on macro-economical indicators. Another significance is its influence on structure. Innovative economy raises the level of education and science. Thus in innovative economy both governmental and non-governmental bodies activity is worth notice.

Аннотация. В статье показано первоочередное влияние инновационной политики не только на макроэкономические показатели и структуру экономики, но и на все области развития промышленности.

Инновационная экономика оказывает ощутимое влияние на вопросы обеспечения безопасности страны, т.к. снимает экономическую зависимость страны от экономики высокоразвитых государств. Поэтому инновационная экономика пользуется поддержкой как государственных, так и не государственных органов.

Keywords: globalization, integration, stabilization, economy, development, investment, national market.

Ключевые слова: глобализация, интеграция, экологическое развитие, инвестиция, национальный рынок.

The wide scope of market relation in the Republic made necessary widening of the innovation in the country economy. So that innovation-novelty or application of the novelty requires production of goods having new characteristics, use of new material, markets and etc. and this is one of the main principles of market relations.

All these require formation of innovative economical development strategy in regulation and strengthening of economical development.

The first significance of innovative economy for government is its influence on macro-economical indicators. The second significance is its influence on the economy structure. This innovative economy influences not only on industry fields but all fields of the science mainly. As a result material and non-material requirements are improved and entirely stimulate development of the nation. That is innovative economy raises the level of the education and science, opens work places requiring more work that is complex. It means higher salary. This innovative economy creates stability entirely in the society.

The investigations showed that world scope innovation projects have so been complicated that even the countries having wide market relations can't realize such projects. And it requires the integration among the countries.

As a result international scientific- technical cooperation is strengthening. This draws the country to from economy stable to the competition.

Innovative economy has a special significance for the country safety. That is innovation reduces depend of the country's goods production technological processes on the foreign countries. With other words it improves country's ability to withstand the other countries' influence.

That's why government regulation of innovative economy has not only national, but also economical significance. From one side innovative economy creates more benefit for subjects and forms condition to indemnify the market's demand and to realize orders, from other side it is not always possible to realize scientific- research results [1, 2].

Above-mentioned characteristics of innovative economy and the State's role in economic and social sphere determine regulating functions of government bodies in innovation process. This task is solved during forming the State's budget by special funds. Thus in innovative economy both governmental and no- governmental bodies' activity is worth notice.

There are strategical goals to the innovations required for the State's interests. With this purpose Government bodies from unit technological environment to provide connection of these innovations together and their joint activity. Strengthening of the competition, also various concessions, awards and other stimulating means are included there. At the same time insurance of innovative risks by the State and special bodies is of great significance in stimulation tasks of the economy. But forming innovative economy also creates some negative cases. The State can play a subsidiary role in liquidation of these negative cases. For this purpose special concessions are determined to increase the interest to realization of the innovation projects in the regions. For example, tax system is used. As a result the State regulates international innovations. That's why formation of innovative economy in the country requires creating innovative economy in the country requires creating innovation policy of the State. And the complex goals and methods from the basis of this policy. With their help the State bodies and the society influence efficiency of the innovations economically and socially [3].

Based on the investigations the State measures in innovative economy are divided into 2 groups:

1. Forming favourable social- economic environment for innovative economy.
2. Direct regulation of innovative economy.

Thus the State's innovation policy is directed to widening competition among the organizations engaged in innovation. For this purpose various normative juridical documents are prepared and realized.

Being based on these we can say that innovation methods of the state are the regulation-influence methods. But the state has also indirect influence methods. Financial and economic mechanisms concern them. Differing from direct methods management by indirect methods requires very little budget. Most of all they cover innovation subject. Such kind of management is shown in the example of Japan. Tax concession can be shown as an example to the management by indirect methods [4].

Multi direction, dynamic and depth of modern innovative project require coordination of the activity of all participants of scientific innovations. In other words general thought is required for all participants of innovative projects. With this purpose they are stimulated by the state to coordinate the activity of all innovative projects.

That's why it is necessary for the State to control these problems in the countries' transition to the market economy and also in our republic. At the same time it is also significant for the state to realize innovative projects in various regions. First of all it significant for the state to realize innovative projects in various regions. It prevents flow of working force into the center [5].

Centralizing all these investigations, we can conclude that in forming main principles of innovative state bodies' economy has to contain the followings:

- Realization of innovative projects has to be reflected in the activity strategy of state bodies.
- The main problems of innovative economy must be coordinated both vertically and horizontally.
- Right and objects of separate organizations realizing innovative projects have to be determined.
- Main directions of innovative policy have to be reflected in the State president's orders.
- Scientific and education commission of Milli Madjlis has to deal with these problems and they also concern Ministry of Cabinets.
- Use of effective innovative potential of higher schools must be one of the main directions of the activity of Education Ministry and scientific- technical problems must be prepared at higher school.

References:

1. Fresztein, N. M. (1999). Transfer of technology and effective implementation of innovations. *Moscow: ANH*, 154.
2. Porshnev, A. G. (1993). Management of innovations in the conditions of transition to the market. *Moscow: RICOLO Megapolis-Contact*, 254
3. Utkin E. A. (1997). Anticrisis management. *Moscow: EKMOS*, 399
4. Suleymanov A. S. (2007). Organization and management of innovation process
5. Utkin, E. A., & Denisov, A. F. (2002). State and regional management. *Moscow: IKF EKMOS*, (320), 6

Список литературы:

1. Фонштейн Н. М. Трансфер технологий и эффективная реализация инноваций. М.: АНХ. 1999. С. 154.
2. Поршнева А. Г. Управление инновациями в условиях перехода к рынку. М.: РИЦЛО Мегаполис-Контакт. 1993. 254 с
3. Уткин Э. А. Антикризисное управление. М.: ЭКМОС, 1997. 399 с.
4. Сулейманов А. С. Организация и управление инновационным процессом. 2007.
5. Уткин Э. А., Денисов А. Ф. Государственное и региональное управление. М.: ИКФ ЭКМОС. 2002. Т. 320. С. 6.

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